

The Sum of Absolute Circadian Shifts: Questioning the Metric Linking Daylight Saving Time Policy to Stroke and Obesity

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We challenge the core conclusion of a recent research article[1] that links the seasonal clock policy to the prevalence of strokes and obesity in the US. Our analysis of the authors' provided code[2] shows the “yearly circadian burden” metric was derived by summing the absolute value of small, noisy shifts, not the intended signed shifts. The sum of the absolute value of small, noisy shifts is not a meaningful predictor for health outcomes.

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In the past years, the seasonal clock policy (seasonal Daylight Saving Time) has garnered significant attention across scientific, societal and political spheres. A recent study sought to quantify the impact of the time policy, claiming to link US “county-level solar light patterns, time policy and health data with circadian models.”[1] Authors' key conclusion was that “permanent Standard Time (ST) would lead to a decrease in the prevalence of stroke and obesity”. With a potential reported impact on millions of persons, the study quickly found its way into social media, news outlets, blogs and Wikipedia pages.

The study's methodology estimates core body temperature CBT every $\delta = 5$ min (1/288 of a day) across one year. Then the time of the daily minimum CBT_{min} is determined. The subsequent step was to compute the daily time difference between consecutive CBT_{min} and Earth's rotation period ($T = 24$ h) to obtain the circadian shift $\Delta = \text{diff}(\text{CBT}_{\text{min}}) - T$. The authors described the final metric —the “yearly circadian shifting”— as the sum of “all the small shifts across the year, including the one-hour shifts in the biannual shifting model, to determine overall yearly circadian burden.”

Only that, authors' code shows that the small shifts were not actually added.[2] Instead, it was the *absolute shifts* that were added to obtain the overall yearly circadian burden (see `computeCircadianShifting.m` lines

192 and 193). That is, every shift added to the circadian burden irrespective of a delay or an advance.

The core methodology might have been sound, if the authors had considered a meaningful threshold above which absolute shifts should be summed. However, authors' code[2] shows a noisy discrete, distribution of shifts not greater than $2\delta = 10$ min, with only significant spikes occurring at transition dates, see figure 1. No seasonal trends were found in the shifts, as revealed by a power spectral density analysis. In the example, the signed shifts across one year sum to zero, irrespective of the clock policy.

The seasonal clock policy is based on a natural stimulus: the varying sunrise times that seasons bring at Extratropical latitude. The magnitude of the solar swing increases with increasing absolute latitude; however, irrespective of latitude, the yearly average sunrise time is 06:00 (mean solar time). The clock policy is designed to imperfectly align working preset starting hours with these swinging sunrise times.[3]

Given this context, the following critical question arises: What meaningful association with chronic health issues can be expected *a priori* if the sum of these absolute small shifts —a quantity that largely appears to quantify model noise— is taken as a descriptive variable?

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Figure 1. The daily circadian shift $\Delta = \text{diff}(\text{CBT}_{\min}) - T$ (where $T = 24\text{h}$) as computed using the script `computeCircadianShift.m`[2]. Shifts are displayed on the vertical axis in units of the model’s time step, $\delta = 5\text{min}$ (1/288 of a day). The circadian period τ is set to the intermediate chronotype $\tau - T = 2.4\delta$. Left: Permanent Standard Time (ST); Center: Permanent Daylight Saving Time (DST); Right: Current Seasonal Clocks in the US for 2023. The location is set at San Francisco, 37.7749°N , 122.4939°W . Note the small, noisy shifts with two prominent spikes corresponding to the biannual clock transitions in the right panel. In this example, for all three scenarios, the average shift is zero ($\sum \Delta = 0$). Standard deviations are 0.90δ (Left), 0.95δ (Center), and 1.07δ (Right).

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AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

All authors contributed equally to this work.

DECLARATION OF INTEREST

The authors declare no competing interest.

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MANUSCRIPT’S TIME LINE

On Thursday 11 September 2025 Laura Chaparro (Science Media Centre España, FECYT) invited us (and others) to make an expert statement on Weed and Zeitzer [1] during its embargo period. A link to the statement

is available at [doi:10.5281/zenodo.17129628](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17129628). We highlighted model’s limitations.

On Saturday 25 October 2025, in the eve of the autumn changing of the clocks in Europe, JMM-O and professor María Ángeles Rol , a chronobiologist at Universidad de Murcia exchanged points of view live on the Spanish public TV. Rol referred Weed and Zeitzer [1] as supporting permanent winter time. JMM-O noted model’s limitations. A link to the exchange is available at [doi:10.5281/zenodo.17440512](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17440512).

On Sunday 2 November 2025 JM suggested to send a comment to PNAS. JMM-O was curious to see the yearly circadian shift for the three choices. For the lack of any graphical material or supplementary information, we inspected the code[2] and found the critical issue (Wednesday 5). We run the code to save intra-year values of the circadian shift (Thursday 6) and completed the Letter on Friday 7, which was effectively sent on November 12.

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